

THE CASE OF MULTIPLE AUXILIARY VERBS IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Yunusova Hilola Ravshan kizi

Ahmedova Muyassar Ahmedovna

EFL teachers of the English Language Chair,
Fergana state university

Annotation. Multiple auxiliaries is a phenomenon which can be attributed to the English language. The syntactic representation of the clause developed by Chomsky and in works derived from his Principles and Parameters framework, nicely explains the well-established observation that clauses in Standard English allow for the occurrence of at most one modal auxiliary in a clause¹. Most clauses contain at least one main verb, and they can contain zero, one, two, three, or perhaps even more auxiliary verbs². The following example contains three auxiliary verbs and one main verb:

*The paper **will have been** scrutinized by Fred.*

The auxiliary verbs are in bold and the main verb is underlined. Together these verbs form a verb catena (chain of verbs), i.e., they are linked together in the hierarchy of structure and thus form a single syntactic unit.

The hierarchy of functional categories is always the same. The verbs expressing modality appear immediately above the verbs expressing aspect, and the verbs expressing aspect appear immediately above the verbs expressing voice. The verb forms for each combination are as follows:

Table 5

¹Chomsky, N. Syntactic Structures. Mouton, The Hague, 1957, pp. 78-79

²Finch, G. Linguistic terms and concepts. New York: St. Martin's Press, 2000, p. 13

Functional meaning	Verb combination	Example
Modality	finite modal verb + infinitive	<i>may be</i>
Perfect aspect	form of auxiliary verb <i>have</i> + perfect active participle	<i>have been</i>
Progressive aspect	form of auxiliary verb <i>be</i> + progressive active participle	<i>be being</i>
Passive voice	form of auxiliary verb <i>be</i> + passive participle	<i>been deceived</i>

English allows clauses with both perfect and progressive aspect. When this occurs, perfect aspect is superior to progressive aspect.

The second class of English auxiliaries, the modals, is unique among related languages. These verbs lack the flexibility exhibited by non-modal “have” and “be”. However, modal multiple clauses often appear in the English speech varying from dialect to dialect. Coleman claims that these constructions are characteristic of the speech of blacks and whites, of males and females, and of persons of all educational and income levels; and moreover, that they occur in informal and formal speech whether casual or careful, as well as in print media, television, and radio. Often those who use them are unaware that they are regional³. Nevertheless, outside of the area, such constructions are stigmatized as substandard and uneducated.

³Di Paolo, M. A Study of Double Modals in Texas English, PhD dissertation, University of Texas at Austin, 1986

The same phenomenon occurs with the auxiliaries in the Uzbek language. Auxiliary verbs, i.e. descriptive verbs (*ko'makchi fe'llar*) following the main lexical verbs (*yetakchi fe'llar*) can come in a multiple form in a sentence. It is considered to be the norm for the Uzbek language when two descriptive verbs come after the converb, yet having three helping verbs in a row is a rare occasion, although such cases occur as well.

1. Elmurod ... dunyo xabarlarini o'qib *bera boshladi* (P. Tursun). – 2 auxiliaries
2. O'tab yalinib-yolvorish foyda bermasligini ko'rib, ko'nglidagi gapning hammasini to'kib *sola goldi* (H. G'ulom). – 2 auxiliaries
3. Kambag'al bo'lsang ham kolxozga qo'sh haydab *bermay qo'ya qol* (P. Tursun). – 3 auxiliary verbs.

In conclusion, it can be stated that auxiliary verbs can appear one after another not only in English language, but also in Uzbek. While in English there can be up to five auxiliaries in a row, in the Uzbek language three auxiliary verbs appearing in one place is a limit.

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